

“I Love Kitsch: (or what the cheap tells us about sustainable design.)”

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Abstract

For any of us who have administered or attended an estate sale, we are very aware of the power that so-called kitsch object holds on our affections. Chalk figures of clowns or Disney characters from the 1930s, trinkets fished from the bowls of gum ball machines, or souvenirs from some long-past fair populate our homes.

What was once sentiment, passes into nostalgia. But at each stage the need to hold tight to the object is strong and palpable. Even if we realize the object is insignificant, the hold of the object on us is strong. What compels us to keep the cheap? We have moved from wall calendars with landscapes by Maxfield Parrish to walls covered by the paintings of Thomas Kinkaid. It seems that we don't live in a world of sophisticated aesthetes. Rather we live in a world where our hearts rule our minds, and where our emotions rule discretions.

In this paper I explore our attraction to the cheap, simple, and sentimental. I look at how even the sophisticated can develop an enduring relationship with kitsch. I examine how the kitsch relationship—far from being simple—is actually quite complex, and how this relationship may hold a key to imagining sustainability.

Keywords: kitsch, empathy, sustainable,

A gnome story

About seven years ago I watched two of my neighbors toil over building a gnome garden, investing good amounts of time, energy, and money into designing an enchanted garden of gnomes. A site was selected (I can only assume thoughtfully in light of their diligence exhibited through each stage of the project). The ground was tilled and cleared of debris. The plants were chosen and placed. When I saw they had completed the garden's construction phase, I asked them about it. They were unabashed in their pride. In telling me the story of building the gnome garden, they freely used the word design. Then they asked me my opinion, "as a designer." I told them I thought they had done a very good job, adding that perhaps a tall gnome might add contrast to the central group of gnomes and make it a focal point.

Now, I have no great attraction to gnomes or gnome gardens. And yet, if I had, my neighbors' gnome garden would be what I would strive to produce. It was not only the care and attention lavished on the initial effect, but the continued care and attention in the upkeep of the garden. The neighbors clearly loved the kitsch oasis they designed. At the time, I wasn't so sure I liked living next door to a gnome garden (could gnome gardens drive down property values?). But I was determined to rise above aesthetics because I liked my neighbors. I recall wondering, rather snobbishly, what compels people to invest so much energy into bad taste? I couldn't think of answer. Now, I am back to think of one.

Aristotle believed that art exists to bring sense and order to our lives. But was a gnome garden art? My college aesthetics professor told me years ago that such things were not art, but kitsch, and kitsch is what passes as culture for the masses. I and my fellow students were told to read (and commit to memory) Clement Greenberg's "Avant-Garde and Kitsch." In that 1939 essay, he famously defines kitsch, and then slams it down. The essay is still being reprinted in art criticism anthologies. He wrote (and I edit here for brevity), "Kitsch is mechanical and operates on formulas. Kitsch is vicarious experience and faked sensations. Kitsch changes according to style, but remains always the same. Kitsch is the epitome of all that is spurious in the life of our times" (Greenberg, 1939). Greenberg's distaste for kitsch did and does influence the opinions of generations of artists and non-artists who are nevertheless well-educated. Even if we, as designers and

artists, don't see kitsch as the concentrated evil seen by Greenberg, we, at least, see it as cheap, sentimental, and (in that wonderfully American colloquialism) tacky-tacky.

And so if I answer as I was trained in Aesthetic class, I say a gnome garden is not art, but kitsch art, which is art for the masses (Greenberg didn't believe that the masses could be educated to understand and appreciate real art; they got kitsch, instead).

But one of my design professors (a great disciple of Papanek) told me that design didn't need to be pretty as long as it was served its purpose. As I think back to my neighbors' gnome garden, Alan's words come back to me.

After I talked with my neighbors about their gnome garden, I noticed other acts of kitsch around my neighborhood and town. There were gazing balls, plastic butterflies on stakes, stone deer and other wildlife, and these were just items related to gardens. These seven-year-old observations tumbled out of my memory along with the gnome garden as I began thinking about this paper. So once again, I canvassed my neighborhood, though it wasn't the same neighborhood as seven years before, and it was in a different state. Once again, I saw a lot of kitsch objects. Art for the masses, indeed. The proliferation of kitsch is a kind of twist on Lincoln's remark about poor people: People must love it because the makers of kitsch created (and sell) so much of it.

Was I seeing something more than just kitsch before me? Was there something to be discovered in the way people put up these monuments to kitsch and then lavished love upon them? There was certainly something more than fashion at work: even after seven years, I saw many of the same kinds of kitsch. What motivated people to expend money and time on kitsch objects and their display? I had found my way to the truth of Papanek as quoted by Alan Tschudi. But were the kitsch objects examples of effective design? I had to find out.

In this paper, I argue that kitsch holds a key to imagining sustainable design. Certainly kitsch is sustainable. Anyone who has spent time at estate sales knows that kitsch collections endures up to (and sometimes beyond) the death of the collection's original owner. If we, as designers, can get beyond our Greenberg-induced prejudices (if any) about kitsch, we can begin to look at the more important issue of how kitsch fascinates so many of us and in such a lasting way.

“Seek not whether a man is a Catholic or a Protestant, a Darwinist or a fundamentalist, a Liberal or a Conservative. Ask him what objects he collects.”

— John Windsor, “Identity Parades”

If he collects at all, there is a good chance what he collects could be characterized as kitsch. Kitsch is everywhere: in our homes, in the antique and thrift stores, and in workplaces around the world. Most of us believe we can spot it without too much trouble. But this is more difficult than we might imagine.

Part of the problem is that there is no indisputable definition of kitsch, and there are two competing viewpoints about the merits of kitsch. On the “kitsch is bad” side, there is Gillo Dorfles (“clichés of bad taste and ambiguity”) (Dorfles, 1969), Thorstein Veblen (“barbaric normal”) , and Frank Wedekind (“the Gothic or the Baroque of our age”) (Hugunin, 2005). And, as mentioned earlier, there is Greenberg. On the “kitsch is OK” side, is Celeste Olalquiaga (“Kitsch is the world as we would like it to be, not as it is”) (Olalquiaga, 2002), Helene Smith-Romer (of “I Due Art 4 You Museum” and her “Pop Alreadymades”) (Hugunin, 2005), and Dave Hickey (and his defense of the kitsch of Norman Rockwell “To enjoy his unique genius all you have to do is relax”) (Yarowsky, 2001).

The long-held belief that kitsch is bad art and bad taste, and therefore, beneath the educated is an unnecessary wall that must be smashed before we can learn from the kitsch experience. Taste is subjective, and throughout history its quality (either good or bad) has shifted with changes of fashion and style, as well as, with what the public will tolerate. “Culture is a process, not a fixed condition,” wrote Levin (Levin, 1988). As we have seen, levels of kitsch exist and are sometimes difficult to discern unless they are pointed out. That is the job of the taste makers and the critics. But their opinions, like the opinions and tolerance of the public, change with time. I want to get beyond this matter of good or bad because it is not central to my argument, which is about the enduring relationship that exists between owner and object, as exemplified by the kitsch relationship.

Levels of kitsch

It is necessary, however, to demonstrate that kitsch exists on several levels, and that there is actually high-culture kitsch, as well as its better known low-culture brother. As I look at the levels of kitsch, I will refer to Greenberg's definition of kitsch since it has been so lasting, and has shaped many opinions about kitsch. I will also use Benjamin's definition because it deals specifically with the copy, and what he perceived as the consequences of the copy.

Using Greenberg and Benjamin's definitions of kitsch, we can put together a short list of what comprises kitsch.

1. It is a reproduction or copy.
2. It is mass-produced, in some fashion.
3. It is emotional. Sentiment is usually connected with kitsch, but there are other emotions, as well, and these run the gamut between tenderness and caring (so-called Sweet Kitsch) and agitation and hatred (so-called Sour Kitsch).
4. It is representational.

A reproduction, mass-produced, emotional, and representational. These characteristics take in a lot of territory. But rather than lump all kitsch together, I want to array it across a continuum, moving from low to middle to high in order to show that kitsch is pervasive across all social classes. I use a continuum since overlapping can occur depending upon the kitsch object.

At one end of the continuum is low kitsch. This is the kitsch that most of us can easily spot. It is typified by the poorly done cast metal souvenir of some famous landmark. Poorly done, but popular, and we buy them, not only for ourselves but for special members of our family and our friends.

Even if we resist the siren call of the souvenir, we can't resist taking photos. These I put near the middle of the continuum because they are original (when taken by us). Yet they are kitsch because they involve some degree of emotion, and they can be reproduced in mass. These images are often poorly composed (showing people with trees and tall building sprouting from their heads), and with bad lighting, cheesy poses, or shameless mugging; in short, kitsch.

Overlapping photos (and just beyond snapshots), are prints and posters. Here we find a glossy 18" by 24" poster of Paris at night, or a Bavarian castle, or Malibu Beach. The

lesser ones situate us by printing the name of the place across the poster in a “culturally-appropriate” typeface. All of these professionally photographed and professionally printed, and all of them kitsch. (Dorfles, 1969)

What about an art print? Maybe a pen and ink of the Governor’s Palace in Virginia’s Colonial Williamsburg (a kitsch reproduction, itself). Or maybe a reproduction of a Monet or a DaVinci or a Picasso? These don’t feel very kitschy, but they are. After all, they are mass-produced copies despite the care taken to reproduce them. (Dorfles, 1969). Kitsch is sort of sneaky, isn’t it? It isn’t just a garden of gnomes. It comes in many guises, and we know without speaking it that we succumb to some level of kitsch.

But what about an actual painting by Renoir? Strictly applying Greenberg’s definition of kitsch—all representation, especially sentimental representation—is kitsch. Renoir has been labeled high-art kitsch by some critics (Jones, 2001). Puccini and Rodin have been, too, because of the passionate expression they brought to their work (Friedlander, p. 378). Of course, Greenberg’s anti-kitsch essay was meant to position abstract painting and sculpture as the only true art. By damning representation and emotion, he drew a very clear division between old art and avant-garde art. Commercial art and design movements, such as Art Nouveau and Art Deco became kitsch, tarnishing the work (and by extension, the motives) of such luminaries as Mucha, Behrens, Cassandre, and Bayer. Looking over some of the above name (and imagining some others that might be included), one might say, “Kitsch? If you say so. But pretty good company.”

Maybe my last point stretches the kitsch argument. I make it to show how kitsch finger-pointing can get out of hand. What is important to note are the types of kitsch surrounding us, from cheap, cast metal souvenirs to fine art reproductions. Celeste Olalaquiaga begins her book on kitsch, “The Artificial Kingdom,” with an anonymous quotation that speaks to the everlasting power of kitsch: “Styles die, only kitsch survives.”

Getting beyond the surface of kitsch

What is our relationship to kitsch? We can find some answers in Csikszentmihayli and Rochberg-Halton’s work, even if it isn’t about kitsch, specifically. Their 1988 study started out seeking to understand the relationship everyday people had with art, only to

discover that people cared more deeply for mundane objects with which they made emotional associations. Csikszentmihayli and Rochberg-Halton found a “psychic energy” that flows between the owner and the object (Csikszentmihayli and Rochberg-Halton, 1988). This leads the owner to expend time and energy on the object. In the Flow State, time is suspended for the owner as he contemplates the object. According to the authors, common objects (and I add kitsch objects here) facilitate flow experience in two ways: either they provide “a familiar symbolic context upon which the owner can reaffirm his identity, or by providing opportunities for direct flow by engaging the attention of people.” (Norman, 2004).

“Psychic energy” turns up earlier in the writing of various aestheticians, where it is identified as empathy. Each of the following aestheticians wrote about art objects. Each of them would probably dismiss kitsch as unworthy of contemplation. However, if Csikszentmihayli and Rochberg-Halton are correct, and individuals invest greater emotion on mundane objects, then I suggest that these individuals contemplate their everyday objects in the same way as described by each aesthete. So I will take what each wrote about the art object and apply it to the kitsch object.

Theodor Lipps found that as a person contemplates the object, his ego unconsciously imagines itself one with the object. This he called empathy, and Lipps saw the observer and the object melding into one consciousness. In some cases, the observer can become so empathetic with the object that he actually mimics the object in some way. Lipps theorized that empathy occurs because the observer doesn't really see the actual object. Instead he sees an object that he has remodeled in a personally meaningful way. He projects this image onto the object thereby establishing empathy (Rader, 1973). Wilhelm Worringer expanded Lipps' theory of empathy, adding to it his theory of abstraction. Where as Lipps saw empathy as flowing from the observer to the object, Worringer saw the empathic transference as a two-way exchange: vital empathic feelings are projected into the object, and then, by abstraction, the beholder withdraws subjective feelings from the object (Rader, 1973).

In his essay, “The Work of Art in the Age of Mechanical Reproduction,” Walter Benjamin laments the loss of the hand-made original. Further, he laments the loss of the aura, which gave the hand-made object its rarefied status (the aura arose from the one-of-

a-kind nature that only an original can possess). For Benjamin, the copy shattered the aura. He saw the copy as cheap, soulless, and ordinary, in other words, kitsch (Benjamin, 1936).

Benjamin, Lipps, and Worringer may not have believed that people could, or even should, have empathetic relationships with everyday objects. But Csikszentmihayli and Rochberg-Halton's study and other like it prove that people do have empathetic relationships with mundane objects (Csikszentmihayli and Rochberg-Halton, 1988, Norman, 2004, Cupchik). The key is the association or associations each person attaches to an object. It may be called "psychic energy" or "empathy" or "abstraction" but it is a deep and abiding relationship between owner and object.

Empathy and analogy for the designer

Empathy is also a necessary skill for a designer who is trying to understand the complex relationship between owner and object. As Alphonse Daudit puts it "you must enter into the person you are describing, *into the very skin*, and see the world through his eyes and feel it through his sense" (Root-Bernstein, p. 182). The philosopher Karl Pepper believed empathy (or "sympathetic intuition," as he called it) was the best way to get new ideas. Cultures are replete with stories of hunters who "became" the intended prey in order to hunt successfully. T.H. White has his Merlin transform the boy (Once and Future) King Arthur into a variety of animals in order that he might become a more empathetic sovereign. Cognitive tests of users are good, but designers must learn to empathize with users, as well. This will help articulate what might be difficult, if not impossible, for the user to describe. As designers, we need to get into the skin of the user in order to begin to understand the empathetic relationship he has with an object.

As empathy is important to a designer, so, too, is analogy. Analogy must be the always-present partner to empathy. At times it might follow the work of empathy. Analogy is what allows designers to interpret what has been learned through empathy. In other words, taking what is learned in one context and applying it to another very different one. At other times empathy and analogy may work together in order that designers may learn about or explain something that cannot directly and physically be sensed. In their book, "Sparks of Genius," the authors, Robert and Michèle Root-Bernstein, write of how

analogies can illuminate previously confusing, unknown, or unsuspected concepts. The authors describe how Helen Keller learned to speak and “see” the world around her despite being deaf and blind. She did this by making “numberless associations and correspondences” between what she tasted, smelled, and felt, and what she could not see and hear. Put simply, she made analogies between the things she knew and understood and the things she didn’t. “I observe, I feel, I think, I imagine . . . I associate the countless varied impressions, experiences, concepts. Out of these materials, fancy, the cunning artisan of the brain, welds an image . . . for there is an inexhaustible ocean of likenesses between the world within and the world without.” (Root-Bernstein, p 191)

Analogies, as opposed to similarities, are comparisons of two or more different phenomena. Similarities are resemblances in surface (in form and color) found in two or more things. For example, “both girls are wearing blue dresses,” or “that boy’s hair is the color of a penny.” In contrast, analogies get beyond the surface, and take us to places we might never have imagined. Analogies build bridges between things that aren’t usually connected through a kind of exercise in synesthesia: “that song tastes like lemons,” “that smell feels like red.” Helen Keller understood that color existed in variety because she built an analogy bridge between color (something she previously hadn’t understood because she was blind) and the variety of fragrances in a flower garden (something she had experienced and understood). In this way, she employed analogy correctly: to reveal, rather than just resemble. One of history’s most familiar analogies occurred when Gutenberg noticed a bridge between a wine screw press and a printing problem he was trying to solve.

I believe that empathy and analogy are indispensable means to help unlock, understand, and translate the kitsch relationship. They offer designers more paths to imagining what enduring and sustainable might eventually look like, but also—and this most important—what they feels like and what they are.

Kitsch and sustainable design

Kitsch seems to offer reassurance to those who collect it. (Norman, 2004). I once worked with an erudite and respected art historian who collected chalk figures. In the 1920s and 30s, these were given away as prizes at carnivals. He didn’t collect them because he

found them beautiful. Nor did he collect them out of a sense of irony in order to feel superior. He collected them because it took him back to a feeling of security when he was young, and he felt safe within the warm bonds of his family.

When I was a boy, my grandmother had a friend who kept a drawing of Martin Luther King, Jr. hanging in her living room. I innocently thought she was related to him or knew him personally. Being a boy who lacked in social graces, I asked her about the portrait. “It gives me strength,” she said. I remember because at the time I didn’t understand how a picture could make you strong.

My aunt hangs folk art reproductions in her eclectic traditional-contemporary townhouse. They are portraits of ramrod-tall colonial couples, and well-dressed, well-behaved colonial children. She says she hangs them because she loves their naiveté. But she also talks about the disintegration of American society. So I think the paintings remind her of the order and correctness of an earlier American society.

And there are my former neighbors and their gnome garden. I did have some history (nine years) with my neighbors. I knew that their sons moved at some distance from them, and reunions were infrequent. Did the gnome garden give them something to watch over and care for, as they once had done with their children? The couple was remarkably good-natured, and the women possessed a wry sense of humor. Maybe the gnomes represented a sense of whimsy. The gnomes were acquired as the couple traveled, and the collection grew over time. Did the couple desired to be collectors? Maybe, the couple wanted to introduce a sense of enchantment in their garden. The swing on their patio faced the gnome garden, and the couple could sit there and gaze upon the gnomes on warm summer evenings.

My point is that with kitsch, it’s not the container; it’s what’s contained. We, as designers, must look beyond the container, and into the meaning contained within the enduring kitsch relationship. This is where sustainability lives.

Going beyond the surface of a thing and into feelings presents us with a very difficult design problem: how do you design a feeling? As designers step beyond the visual, what will be the touch, the sound, the taste, and the smell of each design as we imagine our way through the synesthesia of each translation of feeling? How big is the strength taken from a cherished religious or political leader look like? What is the texture of an ordered

and well-behaved society? What color is familial security? What combinations of the senses will yield the right note of verisimilitude to a design? As noted earlier, I believe empathy and analogy can lead us to imagine using all of the senses, instead of only sight. Left to ourselves, we designers rely on sight ahead of the other senses. In the writings about sustainable design, much has been written about beautiful things: make the object beautiful, as well as useful and durable, and it will be sustainable. I don't quibble with this logic. What I suspect is that those who find beauty in a Jacques Carelman teapot or a Philippe Starck juicer are not the same people who find beauty in gnome gardens. Just as I suspect there are more people who find beauty in gnome gardens than find it in Carelman teapots and Starck juicers. That said, our clients are Everyman and Everywoman.

Dorothy Parker was once challenged to use the word "horticulture" in a sentence. She responded, "You can lead a whore to culture, but you can't make her think." I offer a twist on her quip: "You can lead a person to beautiful things, but you can't make him feel their beauty." Not so funny. But I use it to suggest that we can make all the aesthetically pleasing objects we like, but unless the user feels the beauty, a sustainable bond between him and the object may never form. We can say "this is beautiful, and you must love it," and yet, unless we feel beauty, then it is hollow. It is a bit like Forester's Reverend Eager solemnly pointing out the Giotto frescoes at Santa Croce for his group of sightseers: not even the Reverend felt the beauty of those frescoes.

Let's keep the discussion of beauty in perspective. Notions of beauty change with styles and fashion. Just look at auto design over the twentieth century: from streamline to chubby to tail fins to boxes. I am not excluding beauty from this discussion: Beauty should be discussed: the beauty that flows from the empathetic exchange between the owner and the object. When the discussion about sustainable design begins, let's put aesthetics aside. Otherwise we surely will be led to the inevitable question, "What does sustainability look like?".

Does anyone know what sustainability looks like? I've never seen it. I've seen what passes for it in the futuristic motion pictures and graphic novels of the middle decades of the twentieth century. They show us immaculate cities, free from blight and intelligently planned, unblemished synthetic clothing, and mass and individual transportation that

doesn't foul the air and water. These images have so far turned out to be fantasy. Perhaps this is because sustainability is not an object after all, but a state of mind achieved through the feelings evoked by the object. Recall some of the visions of Le Corbusier and Fuller and other gifted design minds. Their sustainable designs have so far failed to move us to sustainability. Their visions were well-reasoned and rational, but they didn't evoke the appropriate feelings leading to a mind-set of sustainable living.

Now consider the great Gothic churches. We read how they inspired awe in medieval churchgoers. For a moment, let's take a mental walk through a Gothic church. We enter through a heavy, over-size door into an exaggerated interior space. We smell the smoke of the censer. All around us are glittering gold and silver objects. The tall windows of bright colors depict the passions from the stories from the Bible. Over there is the reliquary containing the severed finger of a saint. The church, we discover, is shaped like a cross. We are surrounded by an environment that causes us to know how to behave. No words are necessary; all is known by feelings. Gothic churches were designed to inspire feelings of wonder, awe, reverence, and fear of God's majesty. From these feelings would come an enduring and sustained relationship with the Church. Our Gothic church is a great work of art, and yet it is made up of elements that seen out of context might be called kitsch. I don't mean anything irreligious. My point is the designers of a Gothic Church understood how to use physical things that appealed to the senses in order to evoke the desired emotional response. The objects didn't have to look like an enduring and sustained relationship with the Church, they inspired it.

Sustainability is a state of mind, and this is the greatest lesson we can take from kitsch and its enduring hold on us.

Conclusion

I started this paper in a gnome garden, and I will end it there. As I look at it now, in my mind's eye, it doesn't look as it did to me seven years ago. I watched the building of that garden without seeing any value in the time and money spent. With the perspective of time and (hopefully) maturity, I do. What looked like a simple (and simple-minded) relationship between owners and gnomes has finally revealed itself to be a rather complex one. In this paper, I have tried to show how such a relationship begins and then grows into a bond that inspires feelings of care and sustains itself for a lifetime. I have tried to

show that the appearance of the object isn't as important as the feelings evoked by that object. In this, we see that it isn't kitsch, but the kitsch relationship that's important. And finally, I have tried to show that sustainability is something that must live in our mind rather than in our sight. I haven't seen my neighbors and their gnomes for seven years. But I know that if my neighbors are still there, the gnomes are, too.

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